

The photogalvanic conversion of solar energy into electrical energy in thiazine dye – anionic surfactant system

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Abstract : Photogalvanic effect in a photogalvanic cell containing Diocetyl Sulfosuccinate Sodium Salt (DSSS) as surfactant, EDTA as a reductant and Azur A as a photosensitizer is studied. The effect of surfactant (DSSS), photosensitizer, reductant, pH, diffusion length electrode area and temperature on electrical output of the cell are studied.

The observed photogalvanic potential and photocurrent are 638 mV and 220 μ A respectively. The observed conversion efficiency is 0.8723%, fill factor 0.2794. The cell performance is 85.0 min in dark (the storage capacity of cell in dark). The effect of different parameters on the electrical output of the cell are observed, current voltage characteristics of the cell have also been studied and mechanism has been proposed for the generation of photocurrent in photogalvanic cell.

Keywords : Azur A, DSSS, EDTA, fill factor, conversion efficiency, photogalvanic cell.

Introduction

The use of several photogalvanic systems has been reported in the literature¹⁻¹⁷. In the present work a new photogalvanic system : the Photogalvanic Conversion of Solar energy into electrical energy in 'thiazine dye – anionic surfactant system' undertaken for studies.

Experimental

Azur A (Loba), EDTA (Ranbaxy), Diocetyl Sulfosuccinate Sodium Salt (Loba) and NaOH (Ranbaxy) were used in the present work. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and were kept in amber-coloured container for protection from sunlight. The concentration of Azur A, DSSS and EDTA are 4.4×10^{-5} , 1.76×10^{-3} and 2.24×10^{-3} M respectively. A mixture of solutions of dye, reductant, surfactant and sodium hydroxide was taken in H-type glass tube. A platinum electrode (1.0×1.0 cm²) immersed in the one limb of H-tube and a saturated calomel electrode was immersed in the other limb of H-tube. The whole system was first placed in dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing the platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips), while the other with the SCE was kept in the dark. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations.

Photochemical bleaching of the dyes was studied potentiometrically. A digital pH meter (Systronics 335) and a microammeter (OSAW – A.No. 1632/A) were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system respectively. The current-voltage characteristics were studied by applying an external load with the help of a carbon pot (log 500 K) connected in the circuit.

Results and discussion

Results of variation of dye, surfactant and EDTA concentration and pH on the photopotential and photocurrent of system are given in Table 1. Photopotential and photocurrent increases with increase in concentration of dye [Azur A].

The electrical output of the cell increases with concentration of surfactant (DSSS) with a maxima and thereafter decreases.

With the increase in the concentration of the reductant (EDTA), the photopotential was found to increase till it reaches a maximum value. On further increase in concentration of EDTA, a decrease in the electrical output of the cell has been observed. The effect of variation of reductant (EDTA) concentration shows that the decrease in reductant (EDTA) concentration resulted to a fall in electrical output because fewer reductant molecules were

Table 1. Effect of variation of [Azur A], [DSSS], [EDTA] and pH

		Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)
[DSSS] = $1.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, [EDTA] = $2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 12.71	Azur A $\times 10^{-5} M$		
	3.6	493	160
	4.0	588	180
	4.4	638	220
	4.8	547	165
	5.2	431	140
[Azur A] = $4.46 \times 10^{-5} M$, [EDTA] = $2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 12.71	[DSSS] $\times 10^{-3} M$		
	1.71	512	155
	1.72	605	187
	1.76	638	220
	1.80	584	135
	1.84	475	118
[Azur A] = $4.46 \times 10^{-5} M$, [DSSS] = $1.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 12.71	[EDTA] $\times 10^{-3} M$		
	2.00	321	165
	2.20	323	180
	2.24	638	220
	2.28	615	195
[Azur A] = $4.46 \times 10^{-5} M$, [DSSS] = $1.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, [EDTA] = $2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$	pH		
	12.64	542	165
	12.68	620	185
	12.71	638	220
	12.73	599	160
	12.74	481	140

^aLight Intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , ^bTemp. = 303 K.

available for electron donation to the dye molecule. Similarly, the increased concentration of EDTA also results in to fall in electrical output because the larger number of reductant molecule may prevent the dye molecules to reach the electrode in the desired time.

Photogalvanic cell containing DSSS-EDTA-Azur A system was found to be quite sensitive to the pH of the solution. The system shows an increase in the photopotential and photocurrent of the cell with increase in pH value (in the alkaline range). At pH = 12.71 a maxima was achieved. On further increase in pH, there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent.

The effect of variation of Diffusion Length (distance between the two electrodes) on the current parameters of the cell (i_{max} , i_{eq} and rate of initial generation of current) has been studied using H-cell of different dimensions. With an increase in diffusion length, both i_{max} and rate ($\mu\text{A min}^{-1}$) shows an increase but the i_{eq} shows a negligibly small decreasing behavior with the increase in diffusion length so virtually, it may be presumed as unaffected

by the change in diffusion length. The result are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of variation of diffusion length

Sl. no.	Diffusion length (D_L) (mm)	Max. photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current ($\mu\text{A}^{-1} \text{ min}$)
1.	35	240	230	4.3
2.	40	245	225	4.4
3.	45	250	220	5.0
4.	50	260	200	5.7
5.	55	265	185	6.6

^a[Azur A] = $4.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, ^bpH = 12.71,

^c[EDTA] = $2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$, ^dLight intensity = 10.4 mW/cm^2 ,

^e[DSSS] = $1.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, ^fTemp. = 303 K.

It may be concluded that the leuco form of dye itself is the main electro active species at the illuminated and dark chambers, respectively. However the reductant and

their oxidized product behave as the electron carriers in the cell diffusing through the path.

The effect of electrode area on the current parameters of the cell has also been studied. With increase in the electrode area, the value of maximum potential (i_{max}) increases whereas the equilibrium photocurrent (i_{eq}) is almost independent of this variation of electrode area on i_{max} and i_{eq} and was reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of variation of electrode area

Sl. no.	Electrode area (cm ²)	Max. photocurrent	Equilibrium photocurrent
		i_{max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)
1.	0.25	235	225
2.	0.64	240	225
3.	1.00	250	220
4.	1.21	270	185
5.	1.96	300	165

$a[Azur A] = 4.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, $b_{pH} = 12.71$,

$c[EDTA] = 2.24 \times 10^{-3} M$, d Light intensity = 10.4 mW/cm²,

$e[DSSS] = 1.76 \times 10^{-3} M$, f Temp. = 303 K.

It was observed that i-V curve deviated from their regular rectangular shapes (Fig. 1). A point in i-V curve, called power point was determined where the product of current and potential was maximum and the fill factor (Fill factor (F_f) = $(V_{pp} \times i_{pp}) / (V_{oc} \times i_{sc})$) was calculated as 0.2794, where V_{pp} and i_{pp} represent the value of potential and current at power point, respectively.

The performance of the photogalvanic cell was observed by applying an external load (necessary to have current at power point) after termination of the illumination as soon as the potential reaches a constant value. The performance was determined in terms of $t_{1/2}$ (Fig. 2) i.e. the time required in fall of the output (power) point in dark. It was observed that the cell can be used in dark for 85.0 min. The conversion efficiency of the cell was determined as 0.8723% using the formula : Conversion efficiency (η) = $(V_{pp} \times i_{pp}) / (A \times 10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}) \times 100\%$, where V_{pp} - potential at power point (mV), i_{pp} - current at power point (μA) and A - electrode area of platinum foil electrode (cm²).

Fig. 1. Current-potential curve.

Fig. 2. Power-time curve.

Mechanism of photoelectrochemical reaction in the cell : On the basis of above investigations the mechanism of the photocurrent generation in the photogalvanic cell may be proposed as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

At platinum electrode

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode

where D, D⁻, R and R⁺ are the Azur A and its leuco form, reductant and its oxidized form, respectively.

Conclusion :

On the basis of result obtained in the photogalvanic cell system it may be concluded that value of conversion efficiency, storage capacity and fill factor observed are

reasonable and this photogalvanic cell system can be used in field for solar energy conversion and storage.

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